

Pest management and control OTHER PESTS

Crabs as pests of wetland rice

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Crabs, a noninsect invertebrate pest of wetland rice, cause much damage in West Bengal. The peak season of their activity is generally from July to October. Two species of freshwater crabs have been identified: *Paratelphusa hydrodromus* Herbst. and *P. spinigera* Wood-Mason (family Potamidae). Their presence in fields is indicated by burrows with mud rims around the opening.

The crabs are mainly carnivorous, but they also feed on rice nursery seedlings

and newly planted ones. They cut at the basal regions of both tender seedlings and older plants. The nocturnal pests often carry young seedlings back to their burrow. Heavily infested rice fields may suffer 60–80% seedling loss. The crabs' burrows also cause leaks in bunds and irrigation systems. ■

Snails — a new pest of azolla

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A snail was found to damage plants of the water fern *Azolla pinnata*, which

harbors the blue-green alga *Anabaena azollae*, during an attempt at its large-scale multiplication for application in rice fields. The snail, identified as *Lymnaea (Pseudosuccinea) luteola* Lamarck, is quite common in West Bengal wetland rice fields. Conchlike in appearance, its average weight is 0.3 g. The snail floats in water and adheres to the lower surface of the free-floating azolla. About 800 snails/m² were observed in a heavily infested rice field. The snails feed voraciously on the host, leaving no remnants. Their peak period of activity is from July to October. The snail is not noticed in the field during the dry winter months from November to January. ■

Soil and crop management

Residual effect of azolla application on rice yield

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Field trials on different manuring rates of azolla, both incorporated and unincorporated, suggest that 10 t of incorporated azolla/ha increases rice yields by about 40% over the untreated control and is comparable to the application of 40 kg N/ha as ammonium sulfate. To study the residual effect of that treatment used in three subsequent seasons, the rice variety Vani was again transplanted in the 1978 wet season in the respective plots.

Tillering in azolla-incorporation treatments was superior to that in the other treatments. Residues of 5, 10, 15, and 20 t of incorporated azolla/ha increased yields by 7.7%, 23.8%, 24.5% and 40.1%, respectively, over the control (see table). Inorganic nitrogen fertilizer treatments of 20, 40, and 80 kg N/ha increased yields by 12.0%, 14.3%, and

Residual fertility effect of azolla and inorganic nitrogen fertilizer on rice yields (variety, Vani).

Treatment ^a	Organic carbon in soil (%) at 1978 dry-season harvest	Yields, 1978 wet season			
		Grain ^b		Straw ^c	
		t/ha	% over control	t/ha	% over control
Control	0.61	1.9	—	1.6	—
5 t azolla inc./ha	0.63	2.0	7.7	1.8	7.4
10 t azolla inc./ha	0.76	2.3	23.8	1.8	6.0
15 t azolla inc./ha	0.73	2.4	24.5	1.8	7.4
20 t azolla inc./ha	0.85	2.7	40.1	1.8	9.0
20 kg N/ha	0.67	2.1	12.0	1.7	4.5
40 kg N/ha	0.66	2.2	14.3	1.8	9.0
60 kg N/ha	0.66	2.1	11.5	1.7	3.0
80 kg N/ha	0.63	2.2	13.8	1.7	4.5
20 kg N + 5 t azolla inc./ha	0.68	2.2	18.0	1.8	6.0
30 kg N + 7.5 t azolla inc./ha	0.76	2.2	18.6	1.9	11.8
40 kg N + 10 t azolla inc./ha	0.86	2.0	7.6	1.8	8.9
3 t azolla uninc.	0.69	2.0	4.3	1.9	14.8
4.5 t azolla uninc.	0.73	1.3	2.3	2.1	29.5
6 t azolla uninc.	0.76	2.1	10.3	2.3	40.2

^ainc. = incorporated, uninc. = unincorporated. ^bAt 14% moisture. ^cSun-dried.

13.8%, respectively. Treatments of azolla incorporated with nitrogen and azolla unincorporated gave higher yields than the control, but less than yields from only incorporated azolla. The straw yield of the azolla incorporated

treatment was almost similar to that of the nitrogen treatment; the straw yield of the azolla-unincorporated treatment was significantly higher than that of all other treatments.

Although the organic carbon content